

Incorporation of Latvian gastric cancer patients and control cohorts into the international epidemiological StoP project

Version 1

Description

The project's objective is to generate novel insights and knowledge regarding the risk factors associated with gastric cancer, promote international collaboration, and strengthen the recognition of the University of Latvia. To increase understanding of the significance of risk factors in gastric cancer development, we plan to continue the collection, integration, and analysis of Latvian patient data within the international epidemiological StoP (Stomach Cancer Pooling Project) initiative. Within this project framework, efforts will be directed towards compiling clinical information from the RAKUS (Riga East University hospital) databases, encompassing medical histories, outpatient records, and electronic archives. Subsequently, the gathered data will undergo coding and secure transmission for inclusion in the StoP project's centralized database. It is anticipated that information pertaining to 400 patients will be added to the database. Following data inclusion, endeavours will be made to seek participation in new sub-projects, facilitating epidemiological data analysis and publication authorship. To date, comprehensive data entries encompassing clinical, histological, and epidemiological parameters have been incorporated into the StoP database, comprising a total of 606 gastric cancer patients and 645 individuals constituting the control group. Collaborative efforts with StoP project stakeholders have yielded multiple publications, with findings disseminated through international conference presentations.

Funder

European Commission | | EC

Grant

EU Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No. 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Researchers

Evita Gasenko (0000-0002-4509-6072), Marcis Leja (0000-0002-0319-8855)

Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Incorporation of Latvian gastric cancer patients and control cohorts into the international epidemiological StoP project](#)

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Organizations:

[University of Latvia](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#) | [EC](#)

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Project: Incorporation of Latvian gastric cancer patients and control cohorts into the international epidemiological StoP project (LU-BA-PG-2024/1-0005)

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2024-11-30

4. Templates

Descriptions

Gastric cancer patient data

Identifying of eligible participants;

- o Obtaining informed consent from participants;

- o Gathering demographic and clinical data;

Reviewing of the medical records to extract relevant information;

- o Documentation of patient history, prior treatments, and relevant medical conditions.

Medical information collection from electronic records:

- o Accessing electronic health records (RAKUS) to supplement medical histories.

- o Extracting of diagnostic reports, imaging results, and treatment plans.

Laboratory data collection:

- o Retrieving laboratory test results including blood tests, biopsies, and imaging findings.

Data Management Plan | Incorporation of Latvian gastric cancer patients and control cohorts into the international epidemiological StoP project CC-BY-4.0 DOI: -
29/11/2024

- o Ensuring accurate documentation and recording of laboratory data.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The project aims to generate fresh insights for scientists in Latvia and more broadly, enriching their academic endeavors in the future. While all investigators are currently engaged in research, project participation will broaden their scientific scope, fostering connections with scholars from other nations through the dissemination of study findings at international conferences and through scientific publications.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Survey data
- Clinical data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

200

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

-

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Oncologists

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

MS Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2025-08-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Evita Gasenko (0000-0002-4509-6072)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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